

**ЛІНГВІСТИЧНІ СТРАТЕГІЇ РОСІЙСЬКО-УКРАЇНСЬКОЇ ВІЙНИ:
РОЛЬ ПЕРЕКЛАДУ У ФОРМУВАННІ ЦІННІСНИХ ОРІЄНТИРІВ /**
**LINGUISTIC STRATEGIES OF THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR:
THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION IN SHAPING VALUE ORIENTATIONS**

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The Russian-Ukrainian war has become an all-encompassing event in our lives. It affects not only every man and woman in Ukraine, but also all spheres of our lives, everything we live by and everything we live in. A distinctive feature of the current war is that it is being fought on all fronts and at all levels: from the physical to the virtual and informational, where every word and every symbol has meaning. Language in war is a powerful weapon and an equally powerful tool of manipulation. At the same time, it is a manifestation of ‘soft power,’ which is used to exert a systematic influence on the population's consciousness and subconscious. Therefore, analysing the impact of linguistic strategies on the formation of citizens' value orientations is necessary not only in theory but, above all, in practice. Since the start of Russian aggression against Ukraine, new words and terms have entered our everyday vocabulary, the translation of which is crucial for understanding both the situation and the enemy's intentions, not to mention the fact that manipulative

translation leads to distortion of meaning and the formation of attitudes distorted by enemy propaganda, which ultimately hurts the stability and unity of the nation. Among the neologisms of modern warfare. For example, at the beginning of the large-scale war, the term ‘makronity’ entered the Ukrainian language, meaning ‘to look concerned about a certain situation, but not to take effective steps to resolve it.’ This neologism originates from the surname of E. Macron, the French president, who in 2022 frequently expressed concern, which in turn did not go unnoticed by Ukrainians. Translation plays a crucial role in information warfare, as the same events can be conveyed differently to the audience through ‘wordplay.’ This problem is particularly acute on social media, where a significant portion of society obtains most of its news and analytical information. The research also draws attention to language strategies for protecting national identity, tested by modern warfare, as well as translation as a form of counter-propaganda. The author focuses on linguistic techniques, specifically the use of language forms and their impact on the perception of events unfolding on the fronts of the information war.